

NON-TRADITIONAL LESSONS IN TEACHING PHYSICS ADVANTAGES

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Abstract: *This article highlights the advantages and importance of organizing non-traditional classes in the teaching of physics in the current educational process. In addition, the development of non-traditional improvement methodology was analyzed.*

Key words: *modern technical means, non-traditional lesson, lecture method, information environment, quality, efficiency, innovative technology.*

An important direction of accelerating the educational process of higher education is the individualization of teaching and the development of creative abilities of future specialists. Achieving this requires the introduction of active forms and methods of teaching, the organization of a seamless integration of the educational process with scientific production, and the creation of new and effective forms of organizing independent education of students.

Today, resupplying educational institutions with modern technical tools, information and communication technologies and educational laboratory equipment serves as an important tool for increasing the knowledge efficiency of students. This, in turn, imposes another additional responsibility on pedagogues-teachers. Today's teacher needs not only to know his subject perfectly, but also to have the necessary knowledge and skills on modern technical tools.

Unconventional improvement of the content of a specific subject is important to acquire new knowledge. In this:

- 1) involving students in solving specific scientific and practical problems, creating certain interests in them in this process;
- 2) create an opportunity to perform non-standard tasks that develop students' creative abilities and check their solutions;
- 3) to express the evaluation criteria of the achieved results in most cases.

As a result of this, the motivation of the students and the initial skills related to the subject will be formed. Then every student will have the desire to create a base of desires and wishes necessary for them. In this process, group

members begin to act together. Each student gets the opportunity to enrich his knowledge with the help of the knowledge acquired by his peers. Educational materials enriched with new knowledge will help them in this. For this, the teacher is able to create a collaborative learning environment with a wider use of educational tasks of an intellectual nature [1].

Also, it is important for today's teacher to further improve traditional teaching methods, to consistently apply new pedagogical innovative technologies to the educational process in teaching physics, and to be regularly aware of rapidly developing and emerging teaching methods. .

In most cases, the lecture method is used in the teaching of physics. This method reduces the activity of some students in the lesson and it is known that it is difficult to attract the attention of the listener to the subject and the understanding of the physical processes associated with it. Now, in our opinion, the use of more information and communication technologies in explaining and explaining the topic will improve and increase the effectiveness of teaching.

Therefore, we will think about some conclusions that attract attention to the teaching of physics and technical sciences.

In our opinion, non-traditional improvement is an activity related to the educational process, it is a factor of creating the individual-psychological characteristics of a person, motivation, intellectual development and abilities, a pedagogical-psychological environment in a group and an educational institution.

Within the framework of the topic, we tried to develop a non-traditional improvement methodology:

1. Detailed study of students' individual-psychological characteristics, motivation, intellectual development and abilities, pedagogical-psychological environment in the group and educational institution;
2. In-depth analysis of the sample program of science and development of an applied system from them;
3. Creation of the content, form, tools and methods of non-traditional improvement of the content of the topics of the optics department of physics;
4. Tasks aimed at researching non-traditional improvement of educational content, development of scientific-methodical recommendations, presentation of didactic enrichment materials and preparation of methodical sets based on them, and determination of the level of effectiveness of the methodology.

Placing electronic versions of materials on the studied topics on the Internet is one of the factors of improving the quality and efficiency of teaching. In

the course of independent study, the student conducts a search for completing assignments using the Internet, or the student, who is unable to attend the class due to certain valid reasons, will have the opportunity to obtain the necessary information from electronic sources. This allows the student to fill the gap while creating comfort.

In a traditional lesson, the teacher usually speaks. This reduces the activity of students to a certain extent. The non-traditional lesson mainly allows the student to work independently and actively in the lesson, to think freely and communicate. Teaching with the help of technical tools creates conditions for effective use of the short time given.

Posters have been used as a demonstration tool in traditional classes, but modern information and communication technologies such as computers, slides, and multimedia tools are widely used today. In non-traditional lessons, unlike traditional lessons, the combination of images and sounds increases the student's activity and interest in the topic being taught, and helps to keep the information in their memory for a long time. Most importantly, it encourages each student to work and think independently.

In order to effectively use information and communication tools in the teaching of physical and technical sciences and to use them in the course of the lesson, it is necessary first of all for the pedagogues-teachers to have the skills of working with technical tools[2]. In a word, the teacher should be in regular scientific, scientific and creative research. Otherwise, the effect of the teacher's work will not meet the requirements.

Another important aspect of information and communication tools is that they are the teacher's closest and most convenient assistant not only in the course of the lesson, but also in the process of preparing for the lesson [3]. With these aspects, these technical tools have an incomparable contribution to increasing the effectiveness of the teacher's work.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the use of technical tools in the lesson increases the student's learning rate several times. According to scientific principles, a person receives about 70 percent of information by seeing and observing. In particular, we believe that the wide introduction of non-traditional methods and information-communication tools in teaching physical and technical sciences should become a daily method of every teacher. Only then, we believe that

the personnel we prepare and deliver to the society will become competitive specialists who can meet today's demands.

REFERENCES:

1. Podlasi I.P. Pedagogy. Obshiy basis. Process training. M., 2005;
2. Podlasi I.P. Pedagogy. New course. Fly away. for stud. Vish. fly zavedeniy: v 2 knigax. M., 2002;
3. Topildiyev V.R. Regulatory and legal bases of organization of education and training processes. Year: 2015.